

Unified monitoring systems for fatigue-critical details on steel bridges

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ABSTRACT

The infrastructural transport network of Germany is characterized by a large number of bridges, some of which need major rehabilitation. Especially the rising number of trucks and their higher axle loads have caused an increased damage potential to the structures. This leads to a huge effort for bridge maintenance, with possible restrictions regarding loads and speed or even complete bridge closures. Early detection of possible damage scenarios can counteract this development through accompanying repair or strengthening measures. Ultimately, this early detection can only be realized through structural health monitoring.

Monitoring systems are often a way to ensure the last life cycle period of a structure before deconstruction. Such solutions are expensive and labour-intensive, usually representing purely individual solutions. However, bridges or related substructures of the same design inherently exhibit often similar damage and failure patterns. If convergent monitoring concepts can be developed for different bridges of the same design, such homogenized monitoring systems may be used at an early stage for permanent monitoring of the entire life cycle at comparatively low cost.

In a current German MFUND research project, RWTH Aachen University Institute of Steel Construction has developed unit models for monitoring systems related to two construction types, orthotropic deck plates and steel hangers. These fatigue-critical details were subsequently investigated on bridges using the developed monitoring systems and could be evaluated and compared in terms of their condition. The conceptual and standardized condition assessment can form in future the basis for a facilitated data-based asset management of bridges.

Keywords: steel bridges, structural health monitoring, asset management, fatigue

1 INTRODUCTION

The current situation of the German infrastructure is characterised by outdated structures that need to be adapted to traffic requirements either through repair, refurbishment or even new construction. The older bridges in particular are obviously not designed for the increasing traffic volumes, primarily heavy goods traffic, and suffer from continuous and alternating loads (1).

In order to be able to detect and, if necessary, repair damage, all engineering structures in the road network must be checked for their stability, traffic safety and durability. The standardised regulation of the monitoring and inspection of corresponding structures is regulated in DIN 1076, considering the inspection intervals and intensity to be observed (2). This standard specifies that all bridge structures must be inspected every three years, with every second inspection being a detailed and therefore intensive inspection. This procedure basically enables the detection of all occurring damages and consequently shows the condition of the structure during inspection. The condition of the bridge is then documented and archived in the software “SIB-Bauwerke”. That software is managed by BAST (Bundesanstalt für Straßenwesen – Federal Highway Research Institute) and provides an overview of the entire stock of engineering structures in Germany's infrastructure network (3). However, inspections at intervals can lead to delayed detection of damage, which can

result in consequential costs for increased repair costs and traffic disruption, for example through closures. In addition, it is practically impossible to compare the condition of different bridge structures in the existing data base, as each structure must be considered individually and not, for example, on a type-like basis. This means that it is only possible to determine the urgency of maintenance, refurbishment or additional structures to a limited extent.

2 BRIDGE CLUSTER

Despite the targeted approach for a long-term operation of structures, there is considerable potential for optimisation through digitalisation. That means, that data-based condition and forecast statements can also enable future-orientated inventory management. Today, monitoring systems are occasionally used to monitor structures in order to be able to safely operate bridges for a short and defined period at the end of their service lifetime. It is also conceivable, that these systems could be used also at an earlier stage in order to significantly reduce the intervals of condition evaluations or even make them permanent.

This approach should not only be used for individual structures, but should also provide harmonised measurement systems and comparable characteristic values based on standard models in order to provide a homogenised database. Looking at individual components and structural elements, organised in subsystems and groups of structures and summarised in global structures, statements on condition should enable comparability of all engineering structures. The BrAssMan (BridgeAsset Management) research project has set this approach as its goal in a mFund (BMVI - Modernity Fund) project.

The research project is considering the bridge structures of the associated partners from the road authorities of North Rhine-Westphalia and Rhineland-Palatinate as well as from Autobahn GmbH. At first a selection of structures available for monitoring systems was made and analysed based on properties such as date of erection, type of structure, materials used, vulnerabilities and damages. As a result, clusters were formed in which bridges with the same characteristics were grouped together to simplify the development of measurement concepts. The two selected clusters are those with orthotropic deck plates or hangers and cables. These clusters are predominant for steel bridges. Although these do not represent the majority of German bridge structures, but are of significant importance for the infrastructure network (4). To investigate the applicability of standardised monitoring systems, five structures per cluster were selected and analysed using numerical models. The selected structures are listed in *Table 1* below:

Table 1. selected bridges for investigations regarding monitoring systems

Bridge	Type of design	Cluster:		Investigation:	
		Orthotropic Deck Plate	Hangers & Cables	Numerical analysis	Monitoring system
Rhine bridge Rees	Cable-stayed T-beam bridge	✓	✓	✓	✗
Rhine bridge Neuwied	Cable stayed box girder bridge	✓	✓	✓	✗
A2 Datteln-Hamm Canal bridge	Arch bridge with suspended deck	(✓)	✓	✓	✓
A44 (A1) AK Dtm.-Unna	T-beam bridge	✓	✗	✓	✓
Rhine bridge Emmerich	Suspension bridge	✓	✓	✓	✗
A30 Dtm.-Ems Canal bridge	Arch bridge with suspended deck	✗	✓	✓	✓

The table shows the possible combination of the two clusters in one structure. Bridge support by hangers or cables in combination with a light and filigree construction method such as the orthotropic deck plate is particularly common for long spans. In this way, both clusters can be investigated for four bridges, which considerably reduces the modelling effort for the numerical investigation as well as the planning and implementation effort for the monitoring systems. Only the structures of the Dortmund-Unna highway junction A44 (A1) and the A30 bridge over the

Dortmund-Ems Canal are considered in one cluster only. Another exception is the A2 highway bridge over the Datteln-Hamm Canal. Although it is analysed in the orthotropic deck cluster, it has a concrete composite deck with a steel girder grid. Like the orthotropic deck plates, this frequently used construction design has a combination of longitudinal and transverse beams, the comparability of which is to be analysed with the numerical investigations and the installed monitoring system. Ultimately, two monitoring systems per cluster were applied infield within the research project. The creation, evaluation and applicability of the monitoring systems are explained in detail below.

3 CLUSTER ORTHOTROPIC DECK PLATE

The first cluster is selected for the orthotropic deck plates, which consist of a steel plate and stiffening profiles welded to the underside in combination with a supporting girder grid made of longitudinal and cross beams. Due to this construction, the structure has an orthogonal-anisotropic behaviour, from which the name was developed (5). The general design and an execution of the orthotropic deck plate are shown in the following Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. a) fatigue categories of orthotropic deck plates (6); b) example at the Neuwied Rhine bridge

The load transfer of the traffic loads takes place from the deck plate, via the stiffening profiles into the cross beams and finally via the longitudinal beams into columns or foundations. These elements of the orthotropic deck plates are usually joined together by welding. The welded connections have shown to be fatigue susceptible to traffic. As a result, the weld seams have already been categorised into damage categories, which was adopted as the basis for the research project (6). All welded connections initially show only a local change in component behaviour in the event of initial fatigue damage. Global changes in deformations, stresses or oscillations cannot be detected. The evaluation of the bridge structures and their condition reports has shown that damages of categories 1 and 2 predominates. As category 2 damages are more limited in terms of the number of possible positions, the focus of the investigations was placed on these details, in particular on the connection of the stiffening profiles to the cross beams.

The bridges selected for the research project all have a combination of transverse and longitudinal girders and, with the exception of the Datteln-Hamm canal bridge, a steel deck plate with welded-on stiffening profiles. Pictures of the structure of all the selected structures are shown in the following Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. pictures of all orthotropic deck plates analysed

The undersides of the bridges show that trapezoidal profiles are used as stiffening profiles in Rees, Neuwied and Dortmund-Unna. This is the predominantly used variant of deck plate stiffening. However, there are also variations here, for example in the thickness of the steel sheet or the design of the connections to the cross beams. In Dortmund-Unna, the trapezoidal profiles are welded between the cross beams. In Rees and Neuwied, openings were cut into the cross beams, through which the trapezoidal profiles were inserted and then welded in. In Neuwied, additional openings were left underneath the stiffening profiles in order to increase the fatigue strength of the orthotropic deck plate. In the Rhine bridge Emmerich, two diagonally arranged plates were welded in between the cross girders. Additionally, a halved I-section below was inserted through the cross beam openings and welded under the diagonal plates. As this construction method can be compared with conventional variants only to a limited extent, it was not possible to pursue a monitoring system using standard models to create equivalent monitoring systems. The bridge over the Datteln-Hamm Canal with its different concrete plate is used to compare categories 3 and 4 (shown in Fig. 1) with the other selected bridges. However, the focus of this report will be on the standard orthotropic deck plates.

3.1 Numerical Analysis

To use monitoring systems effectively, the vulnerabilities must be localised first. This was initially done using the damage reports, which are prepared as part of the investigations to be carried out every three years. Ultimately, the monitoring systems were developed on the basis of numerical models that were created for all selected structures. Fatigue load model 3 of the Eurocode (7), or at least individual axes in the case of local or sub-models, were used as the decisive load for the models neglecting the dead weight. In order to determine the relevant load position, the loads were varied in the longitudinal and transverse directions until the stresses in the area of damage category 2 reached a maximum. The load situation and representation of the stresses under the relevant load are shown in the following Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. visualisation of numerical models to determine fatigue-critical positions

All three orthotropic deck plates to be analysed have trapezoidal profiles in different variants as stiffening elements. In the Neuwied and Rees structures, the trapezoidal profiles are inserted through the cross beams. In Neuwied, there are also additional cross beam openings underneath the profiles. Nevertheless, all models show a stress hotspot in the lower area of the trapezoidal profiles or in the connected cross beam area. In the orthotropic deck plates in Rees and Dortmund-Unna, the maximum load point is in the weld seam at the fillet of the trapezoidal profile. Under the load, maximum equivalent stresses of about 150 N/mm^2 occur. The main stress direction is radial to the fillet of the lower trapezoidal corner, which may result in cracks parallel to the weld seam. The numerical model for the bridge in Neuwied shows a maximum stress load at the apex of the rounded section of the cross beam opening. The maximum stress here is around 165 N/mm^2 . The main stresses are orientated tangentially to the fillet, which could lead to cracks perpendicular to the edge of the opening. The details described are therefore all highly vulnerable to fatigue and thus provide a feasible basis for a monitoring system to assess the resistance of orthotropic deck plates.

3.2 Monitoring system

The relevant locations for the monitoring system can be taken from the numerical models. The choice of suitable sensors can also be derived from these models. As the stresses are decisive for the possible fatigue cracks, strain sensors are particularly suitable for assessing the load situation at these points. The measurement frequency can be determined via the loading and unloading speed of the details. This depends on the speed of the traffic. The measurement frequency for the orthotropic deck plate cluster was set at 100 Hz. Recording is intended to take place for two to four years, depending on the structure. As strain gauges cannot be applied directly to the weld seams or to the edge of the crossbeam opening, the gauges must be positioned in the immediate vicinity of the hotspots. The structural hot spot concept is used to measure the stress in the hot spots as realistically as possible. This involves using two strain sensors arranged in series and using extrapolation to calculate the strain of the axial areas (8). Fig. 4 below shows the basic arrangement of two reference points with the calculable structural stress and the sensor arrangement for a relevant detail at the Dortmund-Unna structure.

Fig. 4. a) definition of structural hot-spot stress (8); b) application of the monitoring system in Dortmund-Unna. The stresses calculated using the numerical models have an exponential characteristic, while only a linear stress distribution can be determined by extrapolation. The actual stresses will therefore be higher than the values determined by the monitoring system. Nevertheless, a reliable statement about the alternating load can be generated. Fig. 4 b) shows the application on the bridge in Dortmund-Unna. Here, two strain sensors have been applied in series and in the direction of the main stresses. The distance between the sensor axes and the weld seam is around 15 mm each, as the size of the measuring grids should not be too small. This detailed application was realised twice on each of three adjacent trapezoidal profile connections below the heavy traffic lane. This measuring arrangement was implemented on three consecutive cross beams to check redundancy and, if necessary, to compensate sensors that failed due to technical defects.

The stresses in the welded connection at the selected details of the Dortmund-Unna bridge have been measured over a period of more than one year and the fatigue-relevant stresses were recorded. As fatigue damage had already been detected at the structure with the age of the crack being notable from the damage reports, a notch detail category specific to the structure was determined. This detail category and the alternating load of each monitored detail could then be used to determine the damage per vehicle transit and, as a result, a life expectancy via damage accumulation according to Wöhler and Palmgren Miner (9). The left-hand graph in *Fig. 5* shows the damage to all monitored details of one cross beam over a period of around 16 months. The position of the individual details can be seen on the right-hand side of *Fig. 5*. Traffic changes in the past and for the future are not considered in this investigation.

Fig. 5. a) damage to the fatigue-vulnerable details on three trapezoidal profiles at the connection to a cross beam; b) positions of the monitoring at the assessed details I to VI

The damage per detail calculated over 16 months is around 0.5 % of the total permissible damage for most hotspots. With a structure age of close to 50 years, the bridge can be operated safely for another 50 years with regard to fatigue of the orthotropic deck plates if traffic remains constant. However, the increase in traffic and in particular of the proportion of heavy goods vehicles may reduce this expectation. Attention should be given to detail IV, where damage of more than 2.5 % of the total damage at which weld failure occurs was detected within the measurement period. This high level of damage shows that a particularly large number of heavily loaded wheels have rolled over the asphalt above this point. The quality of the weld seams must also be considered. This can have a significant influence on the damage. Detail I, on the other hand, shows no increasing damage. At this point, cracks were already detected, which prevent force transmission from the rolling wheel via the trapezoidal profiles into the cross beam. This shows that the measured values of the selected monitoring system can reliably indicate damage.

The different development of damage in the summer and winter months is particularly interesting. Damage increases significantly more in summer than in winter. This can be explained by the climatic influences on the structure. At comparatively high temperatures, the asphalt applied has a low stiffness, which means a localised and concentrated load transfer into the orthotropic deck plates. At low temperatures and a high asphalt stiffness, the load distribution of the traffic on the orthotropic deck plate is higher, which is why details are less damaged.

In detail VI, a technical defect could not be rectified, which is why no reliable measurement results could be recorded. Overall, however, it can be shown that the monitoring system developed generates reliable data and allows a plausible conclusion about the condition of the orthotropic deck plate. The redundancy between the three cross beams was confirmed. Even if only a small part of the structure can be monitored, the results can be generalised to the entire structure, as the monitored areas and the traffic loads applied are repeated across the total structure. The measurement results as well as the condition reports of the structure show a consistent condition that cannot be tolerated in the long term. A rehabilitation or new construction must be implemented in the future.

4 CLUSTER HANGERS AND CABLES

The second cluster focuses on linear load-bearing elements that are mainly subjected to tensile forces in the superordinate bridge structure. They are mainly used for bridges with large spans to support the longitudinal structures. They can be manufactured either as a solid cross-section or as a combination of strands and wires. There can also be differences in the arrangement. While hangers are mainly used vertically, cables can be used at an angle. The structures selected for the cluster show a wide range of possible applications, as shown in the following *Fig. 6*.

Fig. 6. pictures of all hanger and cable system bridges analysed

The two Rhine bridges Rees and Neuwied are both cable-stayed bridges with fully locked cables. In Rees the cables are oriented parallel to each other and in Neuwied they are arranged in a fan shape. In Emmerich, the cables to be analysed run vertically and are also arranged in parallel. In contrast to the three Rhine bridges, the two canal bridges use arches, below which the deck is supported by hangers. The hangers consist of a circular solid steel cross-section.

Despite the different designs, all the components mentioned exhibit similar component behaviour. They are subject to tensile forces, which have a static component due to the bridge dead and a dynamic component due to e.g. traffic and weather conditions. The components vibrate in their eigenmodes under the applied load. Due to the dynamic forces, the components are susceptible to fatigue, which can lead to weld seam cracks in the anchoring area or to cross-section reductions themselves. In addition to the fatigue failure consideration of hangers and cables, corrosion, can also lead to a weakening of the cross-section (10).

4.1 Numerical Analysis

Under the typical damage of hangers and cables, the stiffness of the connections or the components themselves changes. The change in stiffness results in a change of the vibration behaviour, which can be determined using numerical models. In contrast to the first cluster, instead of finite element models rather pure framework models are sufficient here. The fatigue load model 3 of Eurocode 3 was also used as the decisive load action (7). The framework model for the Dortmund-Ems Canal Bridge is shown as an example in the following *Fig. 7*.

Fig. 7. a) numerical model of Dortmund-Ems Canal bridge; b) visualisation of hangers with relevant areas of different stiffness; c) first and second eigenmode of hangers

The tensile force in the hangers can be determined by modelling the entire bridge structure. In principle, however, the modelling of separated hangers as a numerical model is sufficient. It is important to accurately model all areas with varying stiffness. For example, the hanger extensions, as well as the connection area to the hangers and the hangers themselves have a different stiffness due to changing cross-sections, as *Fig. 7 b)* shows. All eigenmodes and the associated eigenfrequencies can be determined using the numerical models. However, the first two eigenmodes as in *Fig. 7 c)* are mainly relevant, since all other shapes are technically complex to detect in reality. The following section describes the analysis procedure for the Dortmund-Ems canal Bridge. The four arches used on the Dortmund-Ems Canal bridge have a double symmetrical structure with same sizes and cross-sections. Each arch has eleven hangers with a diameter of 83 mm, the longest of which is arranged in the axis of symmetry. The frequencies determined for all hangers and their first two eigenmodes are listed in the following *Table 2*.

Table 2. first and second eigenfrequencies for all hanger lengths of Dortmund-Ems Canal bridge

length [m]	4.325	8.293	11.380	13.585	14.908	15.350
1.eigenmode [Hz]	25.553	10.037	6.656	5.352	4.825	4.664
2.eigenmode [Hz]	63.562	22.404	14.277	11.283	10.088	9.730

The longer the hangers are, the lower the natural frequency in all eigenmodes. The second eigenfrequency is approximately twice as high as the first eigenmode. The spectrum of the natural modes to be analysed here ranges between 4.664 Hz for the first natural frequency of the longest hanger with 15.350 m and 63.562 Hz for the second natural frequency of the shortest hanger with 4.325 m. These values can now be compared with the measurement results of the monitoring system.

4.2 Monitoring systems

In order to be able to adequately record the eigenfrequencies, two acceleration sensors are required, which record the accelerations transverse to the hanger or cable axis orthogonally to each other. To assess the influence of elongation on the vibration behaviour of the hangers, individual hangers with strain gauges and acceleration sensors parallel to the hanger axis were applied. Influences from the deck plate and the arch were recorded using corresponding additional acceleration sensors. Weather influences are to be determined via a weather station. For the arched bridges, all hangers of one arch were equipped with acceleration sensors. Another arch was partially monitored with the same sensors in order to detect any deviations or redundancies. The monitoring concept for the Dortmund-Ems Canal Bridge is shown in the following *Fig. 8 a)*

Fig. 8 a) monitoring concept for Dortmund-Ems Canal bridge; *b)* applied acceleration sensor on hanger

The sensors were applied at the lower third points of the hangers in order to be able to measure the first two eigenfrequencies (see *Fig. 7*). To adequately record a vibration, at least 20 measured values per amplitude should be documented. Consequently, a measurement frequency of 1000 Hz had to be implemented for this structure, causing a comparatively large amount of data for this number of hangers. The bridges equipped with monitoring systems have been measuring

continuously since 1st of September 2023, designated for a period of two up to four. The natural frequencies are evaluated using a Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) over 10-minute blocks (11). The change in eigenfrequencies over one day is very small. Even over a longer period of time, barely any changes can be detected. The following Fig. 9 shows an evaluation of the eigenfrequencies over four months from 12:00 to 12:10 p.m. for each day. The values show the percentage deviation from the previously mentioned natural frequency determined using the numerical model for the shortest and longest hanger.

Fig. 9: deviation between calculated and measured natural frequencies of the longest and shortest hangers of the Dortmund-Ems canal bridge in x- and y-direction

The deviation is shown for both acceleration sensors measuring orthogonally to each other in x- and y-direction. All deviations are below 5 %, which confirms the validity of the numerical model, even if the deviation for the shorter hanger is significantly larger than for the longer hanger at less than 2 %. Despite the difference to the model, all eigenfrequencies remain very constant in their absolute values. A reduction in stiffness due to cracks or corrosion cannot be determined over this period. A possible influence of hanger elongation due to high temperatures in summer months remains open. The monitoring concept can easily be implemented for smaller bridges. Due to different circumstances, including technical challenges, it was not possible to install a monitoring system on one of the Rhine bridges within the course of the research project. However, the principle of analysing measured values can be implemented in exactly the same way on large bridges and long cables as on the structures investigated here yet. An analysis of the expected service life of those cluster-included elements is not to be expected with the monitoring sensors used. The FFT analysis is limited in its application, as no clear conclusions can be drawn about the specific load changes and consequently no damage accumulation can be calculated.

5 CONCLUSION AND PROSPECT

The results of the BrAssMan research project demonstrate the feasibility of standardised monitoring systems for similar bridge types and cross-structural areas of application. In the orthotropic deck plate cluster, for example, there are variations in terms of plate thicknesses or the design of connections of trapezoidal profiles to the cross beams. Nevertheless, all orthotropic deck plates have similar stress hotspots, which can be monitored and analysed using the same measurement technology. On this basis, it is possible to obtain permanent information about the current condition as well as a theoretical forecast of life expectancy.

A monitoring system has also been developed for the cluster hangers and cables, which can be used for any bridge with these structural elements. The vibration analysis provides information on the current condition of the cross-sections and the associated connections to girder grids, arches or pylons. Contrary to the calculations in the cluster of orthotropic deck plates, a life expectancy could

not be calculated based on the evaluated measurement data of the hangers. But instead this monitoring allows to detect structural changes immediately.

As the monitoring systems that have been developed and are currently used in some cases are individual solutions, there is a considerable amount of cost and assessment work involved in analysing the data. In future, however, such homogenised systems will mean a considerable reduction in effort. In addition, an overall condition analysis of the entire bridge stock will be significantly simplified. Optimisation is required with regard to the large data generation. The high measurement frequencies mean an annual raw data volume of around 14 terabytes for the monitoring systems currently being installed. Measurements at intervals may be sufficient, particularly for the second cluster. However, the potential for optimisation in the asset management of German infrastructure facilities through increasing digitalisation could be confirmed as described.

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